

OPINION

The vaccination lie and why you should get a booster shot nevertheless.

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Abstract

Vaccinated people think they are completely immune to Covid-19 and cannot infect others. This is a false assumption. In November 2020, Europe was on the brink of a triage situation. Now it's November again, a year later, and the situation has worsened despite vaccination campaigns. What went wrong?

A deadly communication disaster

The effect of the vaccines, which are absolutely important, was overestimated beyond measure. In countless countries, there was and still is the narrative prevailing of sterile vaccination, which was sometimes even promoted in government-organized prime-time commercials featuring people without masks at mass gatherings. The slogan was: get vaccinated for your freedom. But it doesn't work that way. Just as there will be no herd immunity. Every medical student should know this by the second semester in medical school at the latest; because herd immunity and coronaviruses do not go together, are incompatible and will always remain so. Anyone who uses the word "herd immunity" in connection with Sars-CoV-2 is incompetent, ill-advised, or has sinister intentions; in the worst case, all of the aforementioned. The same is true for the fact that vaccinated individuals can infect other people, and it happens 24/7, a silent pandemic with catastrophic consequences for the unvaccinated or those whose protection has waned away.⁴

The efficacy data, at least for the mRNA vaccines, were overwhelming when they were presented to the world. But the data basis was thin.² In addition, all vaccines could have been adapted to the delta variant long ago. It had been clear since May at the latest that this would become established worldwide. The heads of Pfizer and BioNTech said publicly back in July¹ that the vaccine adapted to Delta was already in cold storage. That begs the question: Why? What is it doing there? Why is this new vaccine not in everybody's arm?

We believe that this is no technical issue. There is rather the fear that a modified vaccine will require a new approval, this time with manufacturer liability. BioNTech, Pfizer, all the other manufacturers and their shareholders do not seem to want that. Moreover, it may become apparent that some manufacturers efficacy data would not stand up to closer scrutiny.² Moreover, conducting such studies would be very expensive. That's why Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna and all other manufacturers are pushing to go back to using the old products for the boosters.

When the data on the vaccine's efficacy were presented last fall, it was thought that the protection against severe courses was so good that the situation would become manageable. But Israel, the real life Pfizer-BioNTech lab, provided shocking evidence to the contrary this summer. So you could have known if you had wanted to.³

Across Europe, 20% to 50% of all covid patients in clinics are now fully vaccinated. The rate is similar for those who have died. The vaccines are important, better than nothing, but simply not good enough when faced with the delta variant. For those most at risk over age 60, the protection factor is often even lower in terms of severe disease, but the WHO or other respected institution has yet to define a reliable protection titer cut-off.

Nevertheless, we strongly recommend a booster vaccination after consulting your own family doctor.

But beware: there are interesting preliminary prints showing that the risk of infection is lower among the cautious unvaccinated than among the vaccinated who believe that nothing can happen to them. This could also be observed in Israel. Crucially, a significant proportion of those vaccinated over the age of 60 were not properly immune to begin with because they were vaccinated with AstraZeneca, Pfizer-BioNTech or Johnson & Johnson.

Many people were thus apparently only blessed with an insufficient and/or short-lived immunity, which is why all of us should not wait six months before receiving the third vaccination (booster shot), but should think about a third dose after three to four months at the latest. Nevertheless, open questions remain about the behavior of the pharmaceutical industry and the politicians worldwide. But please let someone else tread on this shaky ground. We are just three unimportant physicians.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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